

EFFECTIVENESS OF TALKING PEN IN IMPROVING THE MACRO SKILLS OF THE GRADE III LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This pre-experimental study investigates the impact of the Innovative Talking Pen on the macro skills of third-grade learners. The research employs a comprehensive design to explore real-life experiences, perceptions, and narratives of both teachers and learners within their natural learning environment. Twenty Grade III learners and five teachers from the Division of Misamis Oriental participated, and ethical considerations were taken into account through proper permissions and informed consent. An adapted and modified rubric was used to determine the Listening and Viewing, Speaking, and writing skills results of the learners. While in reading we utilized the Phil-IRI assessment. Researcher-made interview questions are also one of the instruments for the teacher-participants. Initial assessments demonstrated competencies spanning from "Good" to "Average," and "Frustration" in reading providing a foundation for the intervention. After the program, learners exhibited a steady and positive improvement, resulting in an overall average score of "Excellent" in listening, viewing, speaking, and writing, and "Instructional" in reading. Paired t-tests confirmed significant differences, validating the effectiveness of the Talking Pen. The teacher also concluded through an interview that utilizing a talking pen engages students and motivates them to participate actively in class. This study highlights the significant impact of the Talking Pen in improving macro skills, and recommends its incorporation into daily classroom practices. The results demonstrate that interactive and technology-enhanced methods. The study suggests that educators should adapt and invest in Talking Pens, creating a stimulating learning environment where students can participate actively in the learning process. This research adds to the ongoing discussion on innovative teaching tools and their positive

effect on language development, emphasizing the value of keeping up with current educational trends.

Keywords: *listening and viewing, speaking, reading, writing skills*

INTRODUCTION

For effective and meaningful communication every individual must develop the four macro skills of language – Listening and Viewing, Speaking, Reading, and Writing. Macro Skills are the foundation and largest skills that an individual needs to master to communicate and comprehend well. As stated in DepEd Order No 47, s. 2016, Early Childhood learners must always demonstrate the expected competency, always participate in different activities and work independently, and always perform tasks advanced in some aspects including Language, Literacy, and Communication Domains that focus on the four macro skills – Listening and Viewing, Speaking, Reading, and Writing.

In the Early Childhood Progress Report Card stipulated in DepEd Order No. 47, s. 2016 also known as Omnibus Policy on Early Childhood Education, the first macro skill is listening and viewing. This allows Early Childhood Educators to develop the Listening and Viewing Skills of Early Childhood by allowing them to listen attentively, recall details, analyze videos, photographs, pictures, and television, discriminate objects and pictures, and predict story outcomes. In the Canadian Common Curriculum Framework, viewing is defined as ‘an active process of attending and comprehending visual media, such as television, advertising images, films, diagrams, symbols, photographs, videos, drama, drawings, sculpture, and paintings.’ Listening and viewing are essential for effective communication, enabling early childhood learners to gain a deeper understanding of others’ perspectives and fostering empathy. They also facilitate the absorption of information from various media, enhancing learning and information retention.

Speaking skills are equally important skills that an early childhood learner needs to develop consistently as well. As stated by Spratt, et al. (2005) speaking involves the speaker using speech to express meanings to other people. In the same line, Nunan says that speaking is a productive oral skill. It involves the production of verbal utterances to comprehend meaning. In addition, speaking is a social communication that aims at sharing values and traditions that bind a community together (Richards & Renandya, 2002). In the Early Childhood Curriculum of the Philippines, educators assess the speaking skills of early childhood learners by observing if the child uses proper expression and polite greetings, talks about details of objects, and participates actively in class activities such as poems and rhymes. Speaking is crucial for expressing one’s thoughts, ideas, and emotions, fostering effective communication and connection with others. It also plays a pivotal role in academic success, as it allows early childhood learners to articulate their expertise and influence those around them.

Just like the other macro skills, reading is also essential for every learner. Reading is about analyzing written and printed letters and words. For early childhood learners, reading is crucial as it lays the foundation for literacy and language development, helping them build vocabulary, comprehension, and communication skills essential for future academic success. Additionally, reading at this age sparks curiosity, imagination, and a love for books, setting the stage for a lifelong passion for learning. With that, Early Childhood educators develop reading skills by introducing letter sounds and names and interpreting information from books, pictures, and other printed materials.

Lastly, writing is also equally essential for early childhood learners. It helps them develop fine motor skills, hand-eye coordination, and the ability to express their thoughts and ideas. It also serves as a creative outlet, enabling young learners to communicate and share their experiences, which is fundamental for their cognitive and emotional development. Early childhood educators develop writing skills through regular practice, coloring, tracing and even drawing.

As generations evolve, so do the interests of early childhood learners in developing their four macro skills. Young children today exhibit less enthusiasm for traditional instructional materials that educators typically use in their daily classes. Charts, manipulative yet not interactive materials, and other traditional instructional materials are less attractive to young children. Early childhood learners are exposed to technology and that makes them interested in something associated with technology. The study showed that 1234 early childhood educators agreed that using digital technology, such as cameras, video games, computers, tablets, TV, ebooks, internet, smartphones, etc., had a strong influence in assisting learning (Blackwell et al., 2014). In the context of this research, the researcher observed that young children are unmotivated and less engaged in class while learning. With that, it is a great challenge for an educator to look for manipulative materials that are interactive as well and that will assist the learner in their learning even if the teacher is not around.

The researchers discovered the existence of a Talking Pen Learning Tool. According to the Grolier website, talking or reading pen is a thematic learning sequence based on everyday situations and common encounters that focuses on building key language skills such as vocabulary, grammar and sentence patterns, reading and comprehension, speaking and pronunciation, writing, and listening and viewing. Additionally, it provides extensive read-aloud audio that helps boost a child's language confidence. Children can practice independently at ease and in their own time having a talking pen as their guide. In addition, researcher suggests that audiobooks give students practice with accurately tracking text, which eventually leads to word recognition. The talking pen also attempts to teach children the pre-reading skills of letter perception and phonemic awareness on an exercise page of the textbook.

This innovative, interactive talking pen is aligned with Lev Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) and scaffolding theory, which emphasizes that learners can achieve greater progress when they have supportive individuals and tools to assist them, compared to when they learn in isolation without such aid. Moreover, the scaffolding

theory is a learning tool that learners use to advance levels in the zone of proximal development. Additionally, learning tools can also boost and increase their engagement, and motivation, and improve retention. It can help the learner develop certain competencies in a more systematic approach.

With that, the researcher believes that talking pens can provide early childhood learners an aid to master the four macro skills of Literacy, Language, and Communication Domain while learning with teachers and even independently. The talking pen can provide appropriate learning experiences and help them develop and even realize their potential in the four macro skills. This provides immediate feedback and guidance as the learners engage with it. Over time, as the learner's skills improve, learners can start using the talking pen with less assistance and it develop independence.

Thus, this study sought to investigate the effectiveness of Talking Pen in improving the macro skills of Grade III learners from the Division of Misamis Oriental for the school year 2023-2024.

Research Questions

As children are leaning towards a technological world, education must as well adapt to the changes and trends of the generation for better learning. Talking Pen is one of the interactive and engaging materials that children can play with while learning. Thus this study seeks to investigate the effectiveness of the talking pen in the macro skills such as listening and viewing, speaking, reading, and writing, of the Early Childhood Learners. Specifically, this study aims to address the following questions:

1. What are the level of performance skills of Grade III Learners before and after the conduct of Innovative Talking Pen in terms of:
 - 1.1. Listening and Viewing;
 - 1.2. Speaking;
 - 1.3. Reading;
 - 1.4. Writing?
2. Is there a significant difference between the level of macro skills of the Grade III Learners before and after utilizing the Innovative Talking Pen?
3. What are the teachers' feedback on incorporating a talking pen?

METHODOLOGY

Design

This research employs a pre-experimental study design to offer a comprehensive and context-specific examination of the influence of the Innovative Talking Pen on third-grade learners' macro skills. The pre-experimental design incorporates certain experimental elements while omitting others, resulting in an experiment that falls short of being classified as truly experimental. This design facilitates an in-depth exploration of

the real-life experiences, perceptions, and narratives of both teachers and students within their natural learning environment, allowing us to uncover the nuanced aspects of the Talking Pen's effectiveness.

Participants

The participants of this study encompass twenty (20) Grade III learners and five (5) teachers from the Division of Misamis Oriental. This study used a random sampling procedure in identifying the teachers first and later on identifying the participants randomly.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made assessment to collect mixed-method data, to evaluate the effectiveness of the Innovative Talking Pen on the macro skills of third-grade students. In listening and Viewing, the researchers adapted and modified rubrics from Paul Krupakar (2020) to assess the listening and viewing skills of the participants. In Speaking Skills, the researcher adapted and modified rubrics from Shahidah and Umasugi (2021) to assess the speaking skills of the participants. In reading, the researcher adapted the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory. Lastly, in writing, the researcher adapted and modified rubrics from Goodwin and Kirkpatrick (2023) to assess the writing skills of the participants.

The questionnaire's content validity and reliability were carefully considered during its development. To ensure content validity, a panel of experts that included Public School Supervisors and two (2) Master Teachers critically reviewed the items and provided feedback and suggestions to enhance the questionnaire's clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study objectives. The instrument's internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient with the result of 0.87 which implies a 'Good' research instrument', with the obtained value confirming the instrument's reliability and the consistent measurement of intended constructs.

Statistical Treatment

Descriptive statistics, including mean scores, were used to analyze the quantitative data and assess the overall and individual competency-level perceptions of both teachers and students regarding the Talking Pen intervention. Pre-test and post-test means were compared using paired t-tests to determine the effectiveness of the intervention. The researcher also used thematic analysis in the qualitative data from the teacher's interview to find the feedback from the teachers.

RESULTS

This research sought to find the effectiveness of the talking pen in the macro skills of Early Childhood learners. Thus, the results of the data were collected and presented in tabular form. The interpretation was discussed thoroughly in this study.

1. What is the level of macro skills of Grade III Learners before and after the conduct of Innovative Talking Pen in terms of;

1.1 Listening and Viewing;

1.2 Speaking;

1.3 Reading; and

1.4 Writing?

To find the effectiveness of the innovative talking pen, there is a need to find the results of the pre-assessment test and the post-assessment test. These data were considered essential in the way that they provided a clear and transparent impact of the talking pen on the macro skills of the learners.

Table 1:
Learners' Listening and Viewing Skills Results

Expected Competency	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Level of Engagement (10 pts)	5.8	Good	9.4	Excellent
Topic Awareness (10 pts)	4.9	Average	7.5	Good
Fluency in English (10 pts)	3.5	Average	5.0	Good
Non-verbal Communication (10 pts)	4.8	Average	8.3	Good
Listening Span (10 pts)	6.0	Good	8.9	Excellent
Viewing Span (10 pts)	6.7	Good	9.1	Excellent
Total	5.28	Good	8.03	Excellent

Table 2:
Learners' Speaking Skills Results

Expected Competency	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Grammar (5 pts)	1.9	Good	3.5	Good
Vocabulary (5 pts)	2.3	Average	3.6	Good

Fluency (5 pts)	2.9	Good	3.7	Good
Pronunciation (5 pts)	2.9	Good	4.0	Excellent
Accuracy (5 pts)	2.7	Good	3.9	Excellent
Comprehensibility (5 pts)	3.1	Average	3.9	Excellent
Total	2.63	Good	3.76	Excellent

Table 3:
Learners' Reading Skills Results

Expected Competency	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Word Reading	78	Frustration	95	Instructional
Comprehension	52	Frustration	68	Instructional

Table 4:
Learners' Writing Skills Results

Rubrics	Pre-test		Post-test	
	Mean Scores	Description	Mean Scores	Description
Function (15 pts)	7.4	Average	10.5	Good
Format (20 pts.)	13.1	Good	16.0	Excellent
Content (50 pts.)	24.0	Average	34.5	Average
Grammar and Mechanics (15 pts.)	6.5	Average	9.2	Average
Total	51	Average	70.2	Average

2. Is there a significant difference between the level of macro skills of the Grade III Learners before and after utilizing the Innovative Talking Pen?

To find the effectiveness of the innovative talking pen, there is a need to consider the significant difference between the pre-test and post-test assessment. These data were considered essential in the way that they provided a clear and transparent impact of the talking pen on the macro skills of the learners. The table 5 presents the result of the data computed using the paired t-test that includes the four (4) macro skills such as listening and viewing, speaking, reading, and writing.

Table 5:
Significant Difference

Macro Skills	Pre-test	Post-Test Mean	p-value	Interpretation
Listening and Viewing	5.28	8.03	.013	S
Speaking	2.75	3.76	.042	S
Reading	65	82	.019	S
Writing	51	70.2	.086	NS

3. What are the teachers' feedback in incorporating a talking pen?

To find the effectiveness of the innovative talking pen, there is a need to consider the feedback of the teacher-implementer of the talking pen. These data were considered essential in the way that they provided a clear and transparent impact of the talking pen on the macro skills of the learners.

Table 6:
Teacher's Feedback on Talking Pen

Themes	Sample supporting significant statement
Listening and Viewing Skills	<p><i>"Students demonstrate improved understanding of spoken language as they engage with audio content provided by the talking pen."</i></p> <p><i>"Listening to correct pronunciation models through the pen can contribute to improved pronunciation skills."</i></p> <p><i>"Students can recall details from stories/poems/songs listened to."</i></p> <p><i>"They can relate story events to personal experiences"</i></p> <p><i>"They can sequence events from a story listened to"</i></p> <p><i>"can discriminate objects/pictures as same and different, identifies missing parts of objects/pictures, and identifies which objects do not belong to the group"</i></p>
Speaking Skills	<p><i>"My students can talk about details of objects, people, etc. using appropriate speaking vocabulary"</i></p> <p><i>"They can participate actively in class activities and discussions by responding to questions accordingly."</i></p> <p><i>"Students can retell simple stories or narrate personal experiences"</i></p>
Reading Skills	<p><i>"Interactive read-aloud and additional explanations provided by the pen can help students better understand and comprehend written texts."</i></p>

	<i>"It is engaging in the way that students improved their word recognition skills, and their fluency as well. "interpret information from simple pictographs, maps, and other environmental print" "Students can distinguish words that rhyme."</i>
Writing Skills	<i>"Students can write words correctly." "My students have shown little improvement in sentence structure and independence in writing."</i>

DISCUSSION

Listening and viewing are the first macro skills that a child develops. It is their one way to communicate with people around them. In daily life, listening is an everyday activity that has an important role in receiving information (Nushi & Orouji, 2020). Rost (2013) stated that listening refers to a complex process that allows people to comprehend spoken language. Language is a main tool of communication and it is confirmed as a connection of human beings. However, communication does not include only speaking, but also listening which is the way to understand and feel how the conversation or relationship going on (Djabborova 2020). The teacher must incorporate different strategies to enhance learners' listening skills.

Table 1 presents the pretest and posttest of Listening and Viewing. The total mean score for listening and viewing skills for the pretest is 5.28, which falls within the "Good" range. This means that the participants have a good-level skill in Listening and Viewing which includes the level of engagement, awareness of the topic, fluency in English, Non-verbal communication, listening span, as well as viewing span. This implies that learners actively participate in the discussion and show interest in the class discussion, asking for clarifications, and sharing their ideas even before the incorporation of the talking pen. The table also presents that students have a good-level viewing span with a 6.7 mean score. This implies that students can watch certain educational videos. Moreover, the table presents that Fluency in English obtains the lowest mean among the criteria obtaining a 3.5 mean score. This implies that students need to improve their fluency with the help of the talking pen.

Table 1 also presents the post-assessment test results which obtained an 8.03 mean score from the criteria which includes level of engagement, awareness of the topic, fluency in English, Non-verbal communication, listening span, as well as viewing span. This reveals that students improved their listening and viewing skills with the help of the talking pen. Students can interpret and communicate using non-verbal cues. They can learn and talk about the topics. The table also presents that students obtain the highest mean 9.4 in the Level of Engagement criteria. This means that after the integration of the talking pen, students can actively participate in the class discussion by asking questions, and confidently share ideas and thoughts. In contrast, the table presents the lowest mean 5.0 'Good' in Fluency. This implies that students still need to learn more in expressing

their ideas fluently in English. However, despite being the lowest among the criteria, the table also shows that there is an improvement in the student in terms of fluency in English.

The data from table 1 shows the improvement of the students in listening and viewing skills. Students improve their listening and viewing skills by utilizing the talking pen which allows them to be more motivated and engaged in the class. Learning is the development of new knowledge, skills, or attitudes as an individual interacts with learning resources (Karlina et al., 2020). This means that through learning resources, and the talking pen, students can be actively engaged and motivated in class. They are confident in sharing their ideas and thoughts, asking questions, and showing interest in learning from the discussion.

The second macro skill developed in the child is their speaking skills. Speaking skills are not developed naturally. The child acquires and develops their speaking skills from the people around them. What the child hears from their mother, father, or even from the community, is the basis of how the child speaks. Even though the child already developed his speaking skills at home, there is still a need to develop his speaking skills at school to communicate effectively. Teaching speaking has been given much importance at school for many years. This is the reason why most of the competencies in the K to 12 curriculum push learners to perform various activities that deal with speaking such as declaration, reciting of poems, reporting, oral reading, etc. Making the proper sounds, selecting the appropriate words, and understanding structures are only a portion of speaking (Rao, 2019).

Table 2 presents the results of the pre-assessment test and post-assessment test of the speaking skills of the Early Childhood learners. The rubrics include grammar, vocabulary, fluency, pronunciation, accuracy, and comprehensibility which are considered the most effective criteria in assessing the speaking skills of the students (Syahidah & Umasugi, 2021). In the pre-test assessment, it shows that the student obtains 2.63 mean scores or 'Good'. This implies that students have average grammar, comprehensibility, and vocabulary skills, and are good in fluency, pronunciation, and accuracy skills. This implies that students need to regularly review rules in grammar, practice correct grammar in speaking, read books, and learn new words. Students also need to engage in speaking activities in school such as poem recitation and other activities to enhance their speaking skills. This also implies that students still need to improve their pronunciation. Through listening to how the talking pen pronounces the words, students need to imitate the pen. Lastly, the data implies that students still need to practice, improve, and enhance their speaking skills.

Table 2 also presents the post-assessment test that obtains 3.76 'Excellent.' This implies that after the implementation of the talking pen, students improve and enhance their speaking skills. They improve in proper grammar and gradually enhance their skills in using correct structure and word forms. This also implies that students enhance their vocabulary skills and can express their thoughts effectively. The table also presents the pronunciation that obtained the highest mean score from the post-assessment test. This implies that students improve their skills in speaking the correct and clear pronunciation

when speaking in the class discussion. Lastly, this reveals that talking pens helped the students improve their speaking skills which serves as one of the most essential skills of a human being.

Learners can easily adjust and enhance their speaking skills and learn at their own pace through the help of a speaking pen (Tsubak & Maeda, 2020). This provides a supplementary statement that talking pens influence the speaking skills of the students. Regularly practicing correct pronunciation provides confidence in sharing ideas and thoughts.

Table 3 presents the Learners' Reading Skills Results. After the pretest, it was found that the average score for learners in oral reading was 78, while in comprehension it was 52, which both classified as "frustration". This indicates that these learners require additional guidance and support from both parents and teachers to enhance their reading abilities. It is important to note that these learners may currently possess low reading skills. To address this, the Department of Education's Every Child A Reader Program (ECARP) aims to ensure that every child can read by the end of Grade Three (DepEd Order No. 45 s 2002). To achieve this goal, DepEd has implemented various intervention and remediation programs through teachers. The DepEd Division of Misamis Oriental has introduced the Be More Power V 200 reading program, which aims to teach learners at least 200 MELCs-based vocabulary words within 10 weeks.

On the other hand, table 3 also shows the post-test results with a mean of 95 in oral reading and 68 in comprehension both reflected as instructional in reading level. This means that most of the learners can respond to the teachers while administering the Phil-IRI. These types of learners need intervention to develop further their reading ability. It indicates that these learners have average reading skills. It signifies that teachers need activities to develop the reading skills of these learners. These learners can read the passage with a little scaffolding from the teachers or parents. So, they need activities and more time in reading to enhance their reading skills. It could be noticed that in their reading activities, most learners find it hard to read some words in a selection. Teachers still need to explain some words for them to understand. A study revealed that programs like the "Read to Live" program improve learners' reading ability (Sampang, 2023) .

Writing skill has a vital role in learning because it is needed to support the learners' academic success (Aliyu, 2020). Writing skill is a thinking tool for the other three language skills and language components, such as vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar (Khazrouni, 2019). Learning activities using a talking pen can be an alternative method to the learning process. It can make students happy to learn and active to learn (Iffah & Rodyah, 2022).

Table 4 presents the data from pre-assessment and post-assessment of the writing skills of the early childhood learners, particularly Grade III learners. The rubrics contain Function, format, content, grammar, and mechanics that are considered the most effective criteria in assessing the writing skills of the students (Goodwin & Kirkpatrick, 2023).

In the pre-assessment, table 4 presents that students obtain a mean total of 51 or in the 'Average' Level. This means that students still need to improve and enhance their writing skills using the talking pen. This means that students lack exposure to writing that will help them develop and improve their skills. Moreover, the data also implies that students must regularly practice writing from simple to complex to improve their writing skills. This also implies that students must explore and engage their self in materials that would improve their skills. Although they already have the skills in writing or expressing their ideas through writing, the data still shows that student needs to enhance their skills.

Table 4 also shows the post-assessment of the wiring skills of the students who obtain 70.2 or 'Avarge level'. Despite being level at the range of average, there is still improvement in the students as shown in the table. This simply means that talking pen has an impact on the skills of the students in writing. Although it did not have a huge impact compared to the other macro skills, it still showed an increase in mean scores. At the end of the implementation of the talking pen, students can improve their way of expressing a clear understanding of a certain topic. They also improve when it comes to the format of the paper such as the structure that helps convey the message of their composition. The results also show improvement in expressing the clear purpose of the composition. Lastly, they also improve a little in grammar and mechanics that involve the use of tenses and punctuation in written communication.

In listening and viewing, table 4 shows that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the early childhood learner with a p-value of .013. This means that with the help of the talking pen, students can improve their listening and viewing skills. This also implies that talking the pen is an effective teaching tool in developing and enhancing the skills of the students in terms of listening and viewing. Children develop their listening and viewing based on their environment and the usual things happening around them. Developing listening and viewing skills at school requires learning resources such as radio, speaking pens, TV, etc. (Karlina et al., 2020).

In speaking skills, table 5 shows that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the early childhood learner with a p-value of 0.042. This means that talking pens have a great impact on the development and enhancement of the speaking skills of early childhood learners. It improves their pronunciation skills and develops confidence in active class participants. Learners can easily adjust and enhance their speaking skills and learn at their own pace through the help of a speaking pen (Tsubak & Maeda, 2020). This provides a supplementary statement that talking pens influence the speaking skills of the students. Regularly practicing correct pronunciation provides confidence in sharing ideas and thoughts.

In reading skills, table 5 shows that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the early childhood learner with a p-value of 0.019. This means that talking pens have a great impact on the development and enhancement of the reading skills of early childhood learners. This implies that by utilizing the talking pen, students can improve their reading skills, and their ability to recognize words. Abdullah (2018) added that reading can be improved by the use of some activities and techniques

such as skimming and scanning and with the use of technology. Technology can thus play a great role in students' learning outcomes. The results of the Rufaidah et al. (2021) study show that students are better readers in incorporating technology into their reading practices at home or in school.

In writing skills, table 5 shows that there is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the early childhood learner with a p-value of 0.086. Although the data on the writing skills shows improvement in the student's ability in writing, still there is no great difference between the two assessments. This means that students still need to practice their writing skills further by utilizing the talking pen for better results. This also implies that talking pen has a limited interaction with it comes to writing and in more focus on improving pronunciation, vocabulary, and fluency.

After implementing the Talking Pen Innovation, these are the feedback from the teachers as shown in table 6:

Listening and Viewing Skills. Listening is defined by Demirel (2003) as a skill of understanding a speaker's message correctly and reacting accordingly by Ergin and Birol (2000) as a psychological process that starts with being aware of and paying attention to sound and speaking images, continues with identifying and remembering certain auditory signs; and that ends up with making sense of them. In utilizing the talking pen in developing the listening and viewing skills of the students, teachers revealed that student improves their attention and focus by listening to stories, poems, and songs from the pens and actively engaging in viewing pictures from the books. Additionally, students also show improved proficiency in active listening and can listen attentively to stories, poems, and songs. Students also show their ability to recall details, sequence events, and infer characters from the stories they listened to.

Speaking Skills. Speaking is the skill that allows every student to communicate effectively. These skills allow the student to relay information verbally to others. The teacher revealed that speaking is one of the important skills that needs to be improved and developed well. That is why, various activities are implemented inside the classroom to develop the speaking skills of the students such as reciting poems, sharing ideas and thoughts, and narrating stories. With the help of the innovative talking pen, teacher 4 reveals that students can participate actively in class such as reciting poems, rhymes, and responding to the discussion. Additionally, students can retell simple stories and narrate them in the class. As talking pens boost engagement and motivation, students can learn by asking simple questions and talking about details and people using appropriate speaking vocabulary. Students also improve their confidence in speaking and sharing their ideas and thoughts inside and outside the classroom. It also enhances student's fluency during oral activities. It also enhances students' intonation, pronunciation, and articulation making it easier for the teacher to understand the students. Lastly, it also increased engagement in oral activities like poems reciting, and conversation.

Reading Skills. Reading is one of the important skills in language learning (Yu, 2015). It is generally defined as the process of recognition and comprehension of written materials (Heriyawati, Saukah, & Widiati, 2018). In a similar vein, Kasimi (2012), Pearson and Cervetti (2013), and Alyousef (2005) argue that reading is a complex process integrating some cognitive processes, skills, text knowledge, strategic knowledge, and contexts to construct meaning from reading material and interpret the information. In the digital era, students as readers should master the micro skills and macro skills of reading comprehension to comprehend multimodal texts. The reading skills cover micro-skills and macros skills of reading comprehension (Brown & Abewickrama, 2010). With that, through utilizing a talking pen, teachers reveal that students demonstrate improvement in word recognition skills and enhance fluency in reading. This also improves students' pronunciation and articulation accurately and presents better comprehension of the content they read. Teacher 4 stated that students improved their retention and recall of information. Additionally, student increased independence in reading, increased engagement and interest in reading, and can use talking pens to read and explore text on their own.

Writing Skills. Writing skill has a vital role in learning because it is needed to support the learners' academic success (Aliyu, 2020). Writing skill is a thinking tool for vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar (Khazrouni, 2019). Khazrouni further claimed that English writing skill has an important role for EFL learners to develop several skills in their English learning, such as analyzing, arguing, and critical thinking skills. Through the use of a talking pen, Teacher 3 claimed that students can slightly improve their spelling skills and be able to write words from dictation. However, teacher 3 also claimed that among the macro skills, writing skills have the least improvement in utilizing a talking pen. Teacher 2, additionally mentioned that talking pen has helped students gain basic knowledge in sentence structure although it takes time to understand and develop. Furthermore, students develop independence in writing correct spelling and clarity.

Conclusions

The results of this study demonstrate the impact of the Talking Pen intervention on improving macro skills among learners, especially in Listening and Viewing, Speaking, and Reading Skills. The researchers concluded the effectiveness of talking pens in improving the Listening and Viewing, Speaking, and Reading Skills of the learners. Based on the results, the researchers reflect on how tiny interactive and manipulative materials have a huge impact on learners, especially in enhancing and improving their macro skills. The researchers made a realization that learners are more motivated and engaging in class discussions where the trends in their generation are incorporated just like talking pens.

Recommendations

In light of the results and findings in the study, the researchers recommend incorporating a talking pen in the daily class, especially for remediation and intervention classes. Talking pen is an example of an interactive and manipulative material that is an essential tool in developing macro skills in students in this contemporary world. Additionally, the research recommends creating a conducive venue where students can enjoy and engage themselves in learning concepts utilizing a talking pen. The researcher also recommends allocating a budget to invest in talking pens, especially in Early Childhood Children where children need to be motivated while learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To ensure ethical considerations, we have sought and obtained proper permissions from the relevant authorities and secured informed consent from all participants before data collection. The researcher assured them that their responses would be kept confidential.

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